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Green hydrogen initiatives for decarbonization in Europe

Particularly since 2014, European nations who have been attempting to minimize their reliance on Russian oil and gas have been striving in this approach for the last two to three years and have begun to turn to numerous important and tangible alternatives. Green hydrogen holds a unique place among these possibilities. While emphasizing the significance of environmental preservation in their statements and policies, European Union states are launching a variety of measures, both within and beyond the union, to support and improve the utilization and deployment of green hydrogen. This article examines the underlying issues behind the European Union's transformation into green hydrogen, the challenges it encounters, and the initiatives it has undertaken.

Key words: *European Union, carbon emission, green hydrogen, Russia, oil, gas, Hydrogen Strategy, "Fit for 55" package*

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Avropada dekarbonizasiya üçün yaşıl hidrogen təşəbbüsləri

Əsas etibarilə 2014-cü ildən bəri Rusiyadan olan neft və qaz asılığını azaltmağa çalışan Avropa dövlətləri artıq son iki-üç ildə bu istiqamətdə fəaliyyət göstərərək, bir çox əhəmiyyətli və əsaslı alternativlərə üz tutmağa başlayıblar. Bu alternativlər arasında yaşıl hidrogen özünəməxsus mövqe tutur. Öz çıxışlarında və siyasətlərində ətraf mühitin qorunmasının vacibliyini vurğulayan Avropa İttifaqı dövlətləri yaşıl hidrogendən istifadənin təşviqi və təkmilləşdirilməsi üçün həm ittifaq

çərçivəsində, həm də fərdi bir şəkildə bir çox təşəbbüslər irəli sürməkdədirlər. Bu məqalədə Avropa İttifaqının yaşıl hidrogenə keçid etməsinin səbəbləri, qarşısına çıxan maneələr və bu istiqamətdə atdığı addımlar analiz edilib.

***Açar sözlər:** Avropa Birliyi, karbon emissiyası, yaşıl hidrogen, Rusiya, neft, qaz, Hidrogen Strategiyası, “Fit for 55” paketi*

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Инициативы зеленого водорода для декарбонизации в Европе

В частности, с 2014 года европейские страны, которые пытались минимизировать свою зависимость от российской нефти и газа, в течение последних двух-трех лет стремились к этому подходу и начали обращаться к многочисленным важным и осязаемым альтернативам. Зеленый водород занимает уникальное место среди этих возможностей. Подчеркивая важность сохранения окружающей среды в своих заявлениях и политике, государства Европейского Союза принимают различные меры как внутри Союза, так и за его пределами для поддержки и улучшения использования и внедрения зеленого водорода. В этой статье рассматриваются основные проблемы, лежащие в основе преобразования Европейского Союза в «зеленый водород», проблемы, с которыми он сталкивается, и инициативы, которые он предпринял.

***Ключевые слова:** Европейский союз, выбросы углерода, зеленый водород, Россия, нефть, газ, Водородная Стратегия, пакет «Fit for 55»*

Before delving into certain aspects of our topic, I have to emphasize that I believe terrorism, migration, human trafficking, drug sales, wars and conflicts are frequently in the spotlight of people as genuine concerns in international relations, but vital topics like climate change and global warming

are often overlooked. According to statistics supplied on NASA's official website dedicated to "Global Climate Change: Vital Signs of the Planet", carbon dioxide in the atmosphere heats the world and causes climate change. Thus, in fewer than 200 years, human activity has raised the quantity of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere by half [1]. If you need other statistics; According to the UN, fossil fuels, precisely, oil, gas and coal undoubtedly are the most significant contributors to global climate change, **providing for more than 75% of world greenhouse gas emissions and almost 90% of total carbon dioxide emissions.** The sun's heat is locked up as greenhouse gas emissions cover the Earth. As a result, global warming and climate change occur. The earth is currently warming faster than at any other time in recorded history. Warmer temperatures are shifting weather patterns and disturbing nature's normal equilibrium. This presents several dangers to humans and all other kinds of life on Earth [2]. Carbon dioxide emissions have grown considerably since the beginning of the industrial revolution, owing mostly to the burning of fossil fuels. On an absolute basis, **China, the United States, and the European Union countries are the three highest emitters. The United States and Russia have the largest per capita greenhouse gas emissions** [3].

The fact that the European Union states are one of the world's three major carbon emitters explains their emphasis on green hydrogen policies within the framework of the union and making it one of the union's primary priorities. However, I believe that not only environmental reasons but also political factors, are critical in the EU's transition to a green hydrogen strategy.

In 2014, Russia attacked and annexed the Crimean Peninsula from Ukraine [4]. After the annexation of Crimea, European countries were in a rush to take measures to reduce their high reliance on Russian gas; for obvious reasons, the questions had been reignited about whether the EU should keep relying on Russia **for about a third of its gas**, which generated an average of \$5 billion in income for Gazprom each month. The fact that 40% of that gas used to be delivered through Ukraine made the situation even worse for those countries. As a result, EU nations attempted to replace Russian gas with alternate possibilities, such as transporting US gas to Europe and temporarily increasing supply from Qatar. Utilizing renewable energy sources - green energy was also one of the aims to lessen reliance. At that time, the European Commission proposed a **2030 strategy**, which included a 27% EU-wide objective for renewables as a share of energy usage and a 40% reduction in carbon emissions compared to 1990 levels. This contrasted with a 2014 objective of reducing carbon

emissions by 20% by 2020, which the European Union had almost met, as well as a binding goal of obtaining 20% of energy from renewable sources, which was also within reach [5].

Carl Bildt and Martin Lidegaard, the Swedish and Danish foreign ministers, stated in European Voice (now it is POLITICO) that the EU must enhance its energy efficiency and establish infrastructure to promote alternative energy sources along with renewables. Swedish and Danish ministers were actually in a good position to make these points. Because Sweden derived greater amounts of its energy from renewables compared to any other member state, whereas Denmark was the only country with intentions to become entirely dependent on renewables by 2050 [6].

However, not all European countries held the same view at the time. Germany, a European Union superpower, was among nations with especially deep energy ties to Russia and had supported statements from Gazprom, Russia's largest natural gas producer, that Russia had been a stable supplier for decades [5]. **Poland, on the other hand, had been purchasing roughly 90% of its imported gas from Russia,** despite the fact that Poland had been utilizing coal for the majority of its energy needs. Since coal-dependent Poland was reluctant to an early agreement on 2030 climate and energy policies, no agreement was likely to be reached [6], [5].

Nonetheless, we found that the EU nations have failed to take significant measures in the direction of using renewable energy resources - notably, green hydrogen energy - to minimize reliance on Russia. The contributing factors for this, in my opinion, are European countries' unequal conditions and circumstances for the transition to renewable energy resources - green hydrogen, the high cost of organizing green hydrogen, Russia's current level of isolation from European and, in general, world countries only after the Russia-Ukraine war in 2022, and finally, the onset of the Coronavirus pandemic.

When discussing the consequences of the Coronavirus pandemic, it is critical to acknowledge that the pandemic had a significant influence on global energy systems, reducing investments and threatening to impede the spread of vital renewable energy technology. Prior to the crisis, advances in sustainable energy technology were hopeful but inconsistent. According to the IEA's (International Energy Agency) annual Tracking Clean Energy Progress report, just six technologies and sectors out of 46 were "on pace" to reach long-term sustainability targets in 2019. Among the six were electric cars, rail transportation, and lights. Renewable energy sources have shown resiliency in the face of

the Covid-19 issue thus far. **Renewables accounted for approximately 28% of worldwide power supply in the first quarter of 2020, up from 26% in the same time in 2019.** Despite this resistance, growth in renewables was likely to decelerate in 2020. In 2020, the globe was expected to build just 167 gigawatts (GW) of renewable energy capacity, 13% less than in 2019. This drop reflects building delays caused by *supply chain interruptions, lockdown measures, and social distancing norms, as well as increasing financial issues.* Prior to the coronavirus pandemic, low-carbon versions of hydrogen had acquired extraordinary traction. The installation of hydrogen-producing electrolyzers was predicted to establish new milestones in the following years. Furthermore, numerous projects to manufacture hydrogen from fossil fuels using CCUS (carbon capture, utilization, and storage) were in the planning stages or had declared plans to begin operations in the early 2020s. However, owing to the global economic slowdown, supply chain interruptions, and decreased capital investment by firms, which might potentially prioritize other business sectors, these initiatives and other future advances became jeopardized [7].

Now we have to switch green hydrogen and to discuss it deeply. First of all, we have to mention that **hydrogen makes up for less than 2% of current energy use in Europe** and is mostly utilized to manufacture chemical goods such as plastics and fertilizers. **Natural gas accounts for 96% of hydrogen generation,** resulting in large CO₂ emissions. Renewable hydrogen can be produced using electrolysis, **which involves splitting water into hydrogen and oxygen using renewable power (or decarbonized energy)** [8]. It has wide applications in industry (refineries, fertilisers, methanol, and steel), for long-range mobility (trucks, busses, aviation, and shipping), as an energy carrier (green ammonia, or blended with natural gas), and for energy storage in the power sector [9]. Coal and gas hydrogen is already widely utilized to make methanol for polymers, reductants, and ammonia, a crucial element in artificial fertilizers and fuel. However, it is a filthy industry. There is also black and grey hydrogen, which emit 800 million tonnes of greenhouse emissions per year, roughly the same as Germany. **Green hydrogen is an emissions-free substitute that powers electrolysis using renewable energy sources such as wind and solar, leaving only vapour in its wake.** Therefore, it might play a critical role in **decarbonizing difficult-to-electrify industries** such as shipping, aviation, steel, and cement production. However, the concept of a hydrogen-powered green revolution is not new. Hydrogen, the most plenteous element in the universe, was first used as a source of energy in 1804 when Swiss engineer François Isaac de Rivaz created a hydrogen-powered combustion engine via electrolysis [10]. The phrase “hydrogen economy” was

invented by US professor Lawrence Jones in the 1970s, has disappeared, and resurrected several times along with innovations to use it. New Holland Agricultural's introduction of the world's first hydrogen-powered tractor in 2009 is a perfect example. Trials revealed that it could accomplish all of the responsibilities of the manufacturer's diesel-powered tractors while emitting zero pollutants and operating in near quiet. However, it was never commercialized [10].

The International Energy Agency estimates more than five-fold increase in hydrogen demand between 2020 and 2050 to ensure net-zero emissions scenario [9]. Therefore, it is no surprise that green hydrogen will be critical in decarbonizing EU industries when other options are either impractical or too expensive. It has the potential to substitute fossil-based hydrogen in transportation and industrial operations, as well as to launch new industrial goods such as green fertilizers and steel [8].

We observed that European countries regard renewable energy resources - green hydrogen - as a viable alternative, and its' significance in general. Let us have a look at the efforts and plans Europe has done in this regard.

In 2020, the EU adopted the **“Hydrogen Strategy,”** which identified a vision for the development of a European hydrogen ecosystem based on research and innovation, with the goal of scaling up production and infrastructure to a global scale. **The plan investigated how renewable hydrogen production and use may assist decarbonize the EU economy in a cost-effective manner**, in line with the **European Green Deal**, and assist the post-COVID-19 economic recovery. It outlined 20 major action points that would be put in place by the first quarter of 2022 [8]. The European Union plans to construct an investment agenda to encourage the development of hydrogen production and usage, as well as to build a practical pipeline of projects, through the **European Clean Hydrogen Alliance**. The Hydrogen pipeline contains approximately **750 projects** in the Clean Hydrogen Alliance. According to reports, 15 EU nations have incorporated hydrogen in their Recovery and Resilience Plans, **totaling \$9.3 billion** [11].

In general, the EU intends to raise its renewable energy ambitions, **aiming for renewables to account for 45% of the total energy mix by 2030**, up from 40% previously. The European Commission furthermore expects **10 million tonnes of domestic hydrogen generation capacity by 2030, with another 10 million tonnes imported**. It intends to utilize this to replace gas, coal, and oil

in difficult-to-decarbonize industries and transportation sectors. It has put aside €200 million (\$210 million) for this work [12].

I would like to draw your attention to the fact that integrating green hydrogen and ammonia into trading with renewables-rich nations like **Australia, Brazil, Chile, and North African states** might result in imports reaching the region as early as 2024. Green ammonia imports can fulfill direct demand from regional fertilizer manufacturers in **Belgium, Germany, and the Netherlands, which account for more than one-third of the EU fertilizer market.** Remaining imports can be utilized as shipping fuel (directly delivered to boats arriving in the EU's major ports) or divided into hydrogen for use in petrochemicals or steel manufacture [13].

In order to expand the use of green hydrogen, the European Commission increases its' regulatory support for the EU countries. The Commission describes green hydrogen as a “real game changer” and proposes numerous strategies to increase the use of renewable hydrogen as part of its **“Fit for 55” climate legislation package.** “Fit for 55” is an initiative simply called after **the objective of 55% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions to be accomplished by 2030.** The European Commission recommended a 50% objective for “renewable fuels of non-biological origins” - effectively green hydrogen - in the percentage of hydrogen fuels used in European industry by 2030, whether as a source or in primary energy consumption, as part of the plans. However, attaining the EU's 2030 climate objective would necessitate a large increase in the generation of renewable power, which is required to fuel the electrolyzers that generate green hydrogen.

Other goals were also included in the package, such as **a 2,6% aim for “renewable fuels of non-biological origin” used in transportation and additional hydrogen filling stations.** Setting objectives, however, is insufficient to facilitate a transition to renewable hydrogen. “Any aim must be supported with appropriate support instruments for renewable hydrogen in order for it to be economically realistic and competitive,” says François Paquet, who is the leader of the Renewable Hydrogen Coalition. This includes lowering renewable power taxation rates and promoting so-called carbon contracts for difference, or state assistance agreements in which governments fill the gap between the price on carbon on the EU market and the CO₂ price required to make green hydrogen competitive [14].

It is estimated that Europe will require at least 150 GW of renewable energy to achieve its green hydrogen objective, which is expected to help not only phase out Russian fossil fuels but also accelerate the energy transition. According to S&P Global's analysis, wind and solar will account for the majority of this increased renewable power capacity. As a result, the enhanced renewable generation of 45 percent is projected to fulfill the higher objective for green hydrogen, which the EU has highlighted as a key element of the solution for difficult-to-decarbonize sectors such as aviation, marine, and some industrial sectors. As we mentioned above, on June 2022, the European Union Council established its negotiation positions under the "Fit for 55" package that address the energy components of the EU's climate shifting. Several nations and industry players are collaborating on offshore wind and green hydrogen to boost their energy transformation game. To that purpose, the Group of Seven (G7) announced the G7 Hydrogen Action Pact (G7-HAP) in late May 2022, a cooperative endeavor on low-carbon and renewable hydrogen, as well as its compounds such as ammonia [15].

As previously stated, the European Union is not only focused on domestic hydrogen generation, but also on increasing bilateral and multilateral connections with other nations in order to meet its target of 10 million tonnes of hydrogen imports, and India is one of those countries. Thus, recognizing the urgency of climate action, India is placing a major bet on green hydrogen. Prime Minister Modi announced the **National Green Hydrogen Mission in 2021**, in which the goal is to create 5 million tonnes per annum (MTPA) of green hydrogen by 2030, representing a USD 100 billion investment potential. These advancements in India are a significant complement to EU initiatives. Despite the fact that 38 nations, including the EU, have declared or are developing national hydrogen policies and strategies, **only India's goal comes close to the EU aim of producing 10 MTPA of green hydrogen and importing an extra 10 MTPA by 2030** [9].

As of May 2022, 39 bilateral decarbonized hydrogen collaborations had been announced, with **Germany accounting for about a third of them**. Many other European nations, such as Austria, Denmark, France, the Netherlands, Norway, and Portugal are also collaborating, opening up new possibilities for collaboration. **This decade, the EU on its own is expected to invest USD 46 billion on electrolyzers**. Partnership between India and the EU might help to speed the improvement and implementation of low-carbon hydrogen. India's green hydrogen push can have a European pull [9].

Germany, a member of the EU with its' robust economy and industry, also made efforts outside of the EU in this area. The country is attempting to form alliances with nations such as **Australia and those in North Africa**. While Europe has “difficult relations” with nations such as Egypt and Turkey, these countries will produce renewable energy “in amounts much above their own requirements,” according to EU climate director Frans Timmermans. The ideal scenario, he added, would **be to transmit renewable electricity from Europe’s partners into the EU through a cable, but if this is not possible, the energy might be stored in hydrogen or ammonia and brought to Europe** [14]. Germany is also financing 9 billion euros (\$9.4 billion) in the space to assist it transition away from dependency on gas and coal, including **a 100-megawatt electrolyzer in Hamburg, a hydrogen research center in Bavaria with Audi, BMW, and Siemens, and a “hydrogen alliance” with Morocco** [10].

Spain has also taken steps in this approach, via the **HyDeal Ambition project** with a capacity of 67GW [10]. **HyDeal España** is the first industrial application of the HyDeal Ambition platform, which was recognized as **the largest giga-scale renewable hydrogen project in the world by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA)**. In November 2021, HyDeal España was formally established as an industrial joint venture. Production is set to begin in 2025, with total installed capacity of 9.5 GW of solar electricity and 7.4 GW of electrolyzers predicted by 2030 [16].

It is quite fascinating that **Russia might build a new barrier again, in the field of green hydrogen**, which is considered as an option by European nations seeking to lessen their reliance on Russian oil and gas. According to Dr. Max Lacey-Barnacle, Research Fellow in Just Transitions at the Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU) at the University of Sussex Business School, Russia is rapidly expanding its hydrogen ambitions. *“Russia is aiming for 20% of the worldwide market share of hydrogen by 2030, with \$127 million in investment over the next three years and plans to grow into a world-leading manufacturer and supplier of hydrogen energy”*, he states. However, he argues that **Australia is also a potential hydrogen supply for the EU**. According to a recent analysis, South Australia’s excellent renewable energy resources will offer it a competitive advantage in the contest to provide clean hydrogen to Europe via the Rotterdam port [17].

As a result, we can conclude that European countries are presently seeking for ways to minimize their reliance on Russian gas and oil, and green hydrogen is one of these alternatives.

Although the European Union promotes green hydrogen as a solution of safeguarding the environment and avoiding increased use of oil, gas, and coal, as well as lowering carbon emissions, I believe that the political incentive - the Russian factor - plays a significant part here. Thus, Russia's actions in the political arena with these or any other countries, as well as European states' inability to take adequate countermeasures owing to their reliance on Russia for fuel reserves, play a crucial role. To significantly lessen this reliance and prevent Russia from utilizing its fuel reserves to threaten European countries, European governments are pursuing several efforts, either collectively or individually. I already believe that the future contribution of these endeavors - projects will result in the establishment of a new political and economic climate in the region, modeled after the EU, with both positive and negative characteristics.

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